

Role of Yoga in the Mental Well-Being of Senior Citizen

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Abstract :

In the present study, 30 elderly people were selected from Sadguru Nagar, South Nagpur, Nagpur city, by using random sampling method. Doing yoga helps in maintaining good physical and mental health of elderly people. Age is not required to do yoga, only desire is required. Even today, elderly people keep their body and mind healthy by doing yoga. Doing yoga increases happiness in elderly people. Positivity increases, and they do not feel lonely. By doing yoga, elderly people always tell other elderly people of their age how important yoga is in human life. By doing yoga, elderly people do not worry about their future and their physical and mental health remains good.

Key Words:

Elderly, Mental Health, Yoga, Experience, Skills, Lifestyle, Anxiety

Introduction:

According to the 2001 census, the number of elderly people (60+) in Maharashtra was 84.5 lakhs. Out of which 39.5 lakhs were men and 45 lakhs were women. In 2011, the number of elderly people in India has increased to more than one crore. Out of which 46.5 lakhs are men and 53.5 lakhs are women. In 2011, the number of elderly people in India has crossed ten crores. The United Nations estimates that in 2050, the number of elderly people in India will be 32 crore 60 lakhs. Today, the number of elderly people is increasing. Their life expectancy has also increased due to modern Tantra Shastra and medical treatment. Today, the lifestyle of the elderly people has also changed. People are now aware of their health. Going for a walk in the morning, doing yoga, going to

comedy clubs, participating in different activities, doing exercise, such activities help in maintaining the physical capacity of the elderly. Elderly person is a storehouse of knowledge. Elderly person is the key to the house. An elderly person is a walking university. This is the Shidori of rituals. He is a storehouse of knowledge, experience and skills. Drink it for the young, the old, the elderly and the sick and weak. Practice leads to success in all Yogeshwaras. There is no age limit for practicing yoga. Maharishi Patanjali is the founder of yoga. Yoga has been mentioned in Bhagwad Gita. Yoga has been mentioned in the sixth chapter of Jnaneshwari Granth. Swami Vivekananda has mentioned Rajayoga, Karmayoga, Bhaktiyoga in different ancient texts. Patanjali Muni has explained Ashtang Yoga like Yama, Niyama, Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara, Dhyana, Dharana, Samadhi. Yoga is a way of life. The Sanskrit word 'yuj' is made from metal. Yu jiane 'yuj' means to join. Joining means to integrate. Yoga joins body and mind. It joins soul and God. Yoga joins person to person.

Yoga is mentioned in the oldest literature Vedas. Yoga is also mentioned in Upanishads. In many books like Hathapradeepika, Gherandasahita, Shivasamhita, the process of asana, bandha, mudra, pranayama, purification, meditation has been described. Yogaschittavritti nirodhah. Yoga means the control of the mind's mind. The mind of a person is fickle. Yoga controls the fickle mind of a person. 'Yoga: Manah Prashamana Upayah'. Yoga means the method of controlling the mind with effort. In today's age of globalization, human life is on the move. Because of this fast life, instability has increased. This unstable mind needs peace and stability today. Peace of mind, mental health can be achieved only by practicing yoga.

Objectives of Study:

- 1) To study the mental health of elderly people.
- 2) To study the positivity in elderly people due to yoga.

Area of Study:

In the present study, the area of Sadguru Nagar in South Nagpur of Nagpur city has been taken for study.

Sample Method and Data Collection:

30 elderly people were selected from Sadguru Nagar in South Nagpur of Nagpur city by using non-probability sampling method using random sampling method. Data has been collected by selecting interview schedule using primary data collection method. In the secondary data collection method, monthly, internet, articles, newspapers have been used.

Data Interpretation and Analysis:

Yoga is a way of life. Elderly people do pranayama, meditation, yoga asanas. Elderly people wake up in the morning by doing yoga. They do Suryanamaskar every day. Elderly people do not like to do yoga if they have never done it. Elderly people always remain active by doing yoga. People practice Ashtanga Yoga in their lives. Elderly people do yoga slowly and at a slow pace. Elderly people who have done yoga regularly did not get corona. Elderly people do such active activities that would make the youth feel ashamed. Elderly people do yoga according to their health. Santoshadanuttam Sukhlabh. Elderly people benefit from satisfaction in their lives by doing yoga. Some elderly people do not fear anything by doing yoga. They fight any situation fearlessly. By doing yoga, you have to meet many people. The acquaintance with new people has increased. Due to the yoga program, one has to participate in many yoga activities, due to which the activity of participating in online programs has also increased. The loneliness that was felt due to old age has been reduced due to yoga by increasing social contact. Due to yoga, the immunity of the elderly has increased. Due to doing yoga, there has been a positive change in the lifestyle of the elderly. There has been a good change in the daily routine. The atmosphere of the family has also become positive. The family members are happy due to this positive thinking of the elderly. There is only joy in the family. Due to yoga, the contact of the elderly with the community has increased.

By doing yoga, the elderly have got emotional control. The elderly have learned to control negative thoughts. Yoga helps in keeping the mental health of the elderly good. Due to yoga, the worries of the elderly have reduced. By doing yoga, the elderly have started sleeping well. There is no problem related to sleep. The more a person does yoga among the elderly, the more benefits he will get; because of this the elderly people do yoga daily

Conclusion:

- By doing yoga, the mental health of the elderly is good.
- Due to doing yoga, the elderly still have fitness, energy, and the desire to work.
- The elderly tell others about the importance of yoga.
- The elderly want to spend their future life completely in yoga.
- By doing yoga, mental health problems are seen less in elderly people.
- By doing yoga, problems related to despair, failure, fear, insomnia are seen less in elderly people.
- By doing yoga, there is more enthusiasm in elderly people.
- By doing yoga, elderly people always think positive and also give the message of positive thinking to the family members.

Suggestions and Recommendation:

- Elderly men and women should both do yoga for their physical and mental health.
- Corporator of every ward should organize free yoga camps for elderly people in his ward.
- Lectures by experts should be organized to explain how yoga changes in the body and mind.
- Elderly people who teach yoga should be appointed to teach yoga to children and youth.

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